

Musculoskeletal Occupational Hazards And Physiotherapy Awareness In A Rural Setting Of North India: A Short Survey Report

Sharwani Jha¹

MPT Student, Department of Physiotherapy,
Sharda Hospital, Sharda University, Plot No.32, 34,
Knowledge Park III, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh.

Received: 12th Feb. 2026

Revised: 01st May. 2026

Accepted: 15th May. 2026

Mayank Shukla²

Professor & Head Physiotherapy, Department of Physiotherapy,
Sharda Hospital, Sharda University, Plot No 32, 34,
Knowledge Park III, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh.
Email - mailmayankshukla@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Background: This study aimed to evaluate the prevalence of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) associated with occupational hazards in a rural population, and assess the levels of awareness, knowledge, and utilization of physiotherapy services, further to identify barriers hindering access to non-pharmacological pain management within the community.

Materials and Methods: A cross-sectional survey design was employed over a two-week period in the rural setting of Nawada, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India. A total of 15 participants (8 male, 7 female) engaged in physically demanding, low-income occupations were recruited. Data were collected using structured questionnaires focusing on demographics, occupational factors, the occurrence and site of body pain, physiotherapy awareness, and initial pain management strategies. A subsequent educational awareness session was provided to all participants.

Results: Only 33% of respondents had prior knowledge of the profession or its services. Pain prevalence was high, with the most reported sites being multiple joints (44%) and the spine (31%), directly correlating with physically demanding work profiles (35.2% self-employed, 29.4% daily wages). The initial treatment approach showed a strong dependence on self-medication: 53% relied on pain killers, while utilization of formal physiotherapy services was 0%.

Discussion: The findings indicated a critically low level of physiotherapy awareness among individuals having musculoskeletal complaints, with poor knowledge and absolutely no utilization of it. This deficit results in a reliance on short-term pharmacological interventions (pain killers) for chronic, occupation-induced MSDs, thus neglecting definitive rehabilitative care. The findings strongly suggest the need for targeted community education and the integration of physiotherapy into rural primary healthcare systems to enhance health outcomes and functional capacity among the working population.

Conclusion: The awareness and accessibility of physiotherapy services in the surveyed rural community are severely limited. Widespread use of self-medication with painkillers is seen. Rural physiotherapy services in the studied area require strengthening.

Keywords: Physiotherapy Awareness, Musculoskeletal Disorders, Occupational Health, Rural Community, Pain Management.

INTRODUCTION

Musculoskeletal disorders are among the leading causes of pain, disability, and reduced productivity worldwide. They affect individuals across all age groups and

occupational sectors, with an especially high prevalence among manual labourers and agricultural workers in rural areas (Melariri et al., 2021).¹ In India, where a large segment of the population resides in villages and depends on physically demanding occupations,

musculoskeletal pain arising from occupational hazards is a significant yet often neglected health concern (Ssemata et al., 2024).² Despite strong evidence that physiotherapy interventions such as exercise therapy, posture correction, and ergonomic education can effectively alleviate pain and improve functional ability, awareness, and utilization of these services remain limited in rural communities. The rural population faces multiple barriers in accessing physiotherapy services, e.g. a lack of nearby clinics, insufficient referral systems, limited availability of trained physiotherapists, and inadequate knowledge about the benefits of physiotherapy mainly with alized populations (Dash, 2019).³ As a result, individuals rely on self- 'medication or traditional remedies for pain management, which offers temporary relief without addressing the underlying cause. Studies from various parts of India have consistently shown that awareness of physiotherapy is higher in urban areas compared to rural regions, and even among rural health profession.

In rural communities, musculoskeletal pain is often managed with self- medication and painkillers due to poor awareness and accessibility of physiotherapy services, even in students (Mulerpattn et al., 2022).⁵ Such reports are available from international studies as well. and knowledge of different society members is emphasized.⁶ Researchers emphasize the need for educational interventions and community-based awareness programs to bridge this knowledge gap and promote physiotherapy as an effective, non-pharmacological approach.

OBJECTIVES

- To identify and analyze the occupational factors contributing to the development of musculoskeletal disorders in rural populations.
- To assess the level of awareness, knowledge, and perception regarding physiotherapy and its role in the management of musculoskeletal conditions.

- To identify key barriers social, economic, infrastructural, and informational that hinder the use of physiotherapy services in rural areas.
- To propose recommendations aimed at enhancing physiotherapy awareness, accessibility, and integrity.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

In rural communities, musculoskeletal pain is often managed with self- medication and painkillers due to poor awareness and accessibility of physiotherapy services. Researchers emphasize the need for educational interventions and community-based awareness programs to bridge this knowledge gap and promote physiotherapy as an effective, non- pharmacological approach.

Fernandes et al., (2024)⁴, in rural Goa identified key barriers to accessing physiotherapy services for musculoskeletal disorders. The authors reported that although 74% of participants were aware of physiotherapy, only 12% had access to local clinics, and 18% relied on traditional medicine. Among healthcare workers, 96% were aware of physiotherapy, yet cited lack of clinics, poor referrals, and insufficient resources as major obstacles. The study exhibited that despite moderate awareness, limited infrastructure and inadequate resource allocation significantly hinder physiotherapy service delivery in rural areas, emphasizing the need for improved accessibility and integration of rehabilitation services into rural healthcare systems.

Ramanandi et al., (2019)⁸ conducted in four major cities of Gujarat—Ahmedabad, Vadodara, Rajkot, and Surat—assessed the awareness, attitude, belief, and utilization of physiotherapy services among 500 members of the general public. The findings revealed that 85.4% of participants were aware of physiotherapy and 87.2% were familiar with its services, primarily associating it with the treatment of bone and joint disorders (67.4%). Nearly half (49.5%) believed physiotherapy to be shown that awareness of physiotherapy is significantly higher in urban populations

compared to rural areas, where misconceptions and limited access remain common. Education plays a crucial role, as individuals with higher qualifications demonstrate better understanding and acceptance of physiotherapy than those with lower education levels.

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

Study Design: Cross-sectional survey study

Sampling Method: Survey

Duration: 2 weeks, Study setting: Nawada, Greater Noida — 201310, Uttar Pradesh, India

Participation: 15 Male: 8 Female: 7 A series of questions in the form of questionnaires were asked related to physiotherapy awareness in the community and prevalence of musculoskeletal pain and initial treatment approaches. After taking the data, an awareness session was held to educate participants about the role of physiotherapy in preventing and managing musculoskeletal disorders, where emphasizing in simple exercises, posture corrections, ergonomics practices, and the long-term benefits of physiotherapy. All parameters have content validity.

RESULTS

The collected data was analysed and presented in tables. The data showed a level of

awareness. Of the 15 households, 8 (53.3%) were male and 46.6% were female. The majority of participants (33.3%) were between the ages of 26 and 35, with only 13.3% falling between the ages of 18 and 25. The data obtained revealed that only a small percentage of participants (33%) had heard of and understood physiotherapy, while more than half of the population (67%) had never heard about it. People who were familiar with physiotherapists and their work learned about them through a variety of sources, including hospitals (20%), primary health care (40%), social media (20%), and other-(20%). Questions were asked about areas of pain in the body during functional activity, and the data revealed that the majority of participants (44%) had pain in multiple joints, followed by the spine (31%), lower limb (13%), and very few in the upper limb (12%). The initial treatment received for body pain data was obtained and revealed the highest dependence on painkillers (53%) followed by massage (26%), hot water and balm (21%), and physiotherapy (0%), indicating that participants are unaware of physiotherapy and lack knowledge of exercise therapy to relieve pain. The data revealed that people living in rural areas have a low level of awareness about physiotherapy and its pain management techniques.

Table 1: Demographic & Descriptive statistics of the sample in the survey

Characteristic	Category	N (Count)	% (Percentage)
Age (years)	18-25	2	13.3
	26-35	5	33.3
	36-45	3	20
	46-60	1	6.66
	60+	5	33.3
Gender	Female	7	46.6
	Male	8	53.3
Source Of Income(Family)	Daily wages	5	29.4
	Self-employed	6	35.2
	Salaried job	2	11.7
	Govt. Assistance	1	5.8
	Other	3	17.6

Table 2: Sources of information about knowledge, awareness and utilization of physiotherapy

Variable	Frequency(n)	N%
Hospital	1	20
Primary HealthCare	2	40
Social Media	1	20
Others	1	20

DISCUSSION

The goal of this study was to determine the level of awareness of physiotherapy among rural residents and to better understand their approaches to managing musculoskeletal pain.

Main Findings: Due to India's vast geographical and cultural diversity, there is a significant difference in knowledge levels between rural and urban areas.⁴ The study found that because the majority of people in rural areas have a low source of income, they frequently lack the freedom to choose less strenuous jobs and are forced to work long hours in harsh conditions without any occupational safety measures, health insurance, or government schemes, resulting in frequent musculoskeletal pain, fatigue, and body pain.⁴

The findings of this study show that only 33% of the rural population is aware of physiotherapy. The remaining 67% have never heard of physiotherapy and its components. The figure in this study shows a low level of awareness about physiotherapy among individuals living in rural areas, as well as various multiple level joint pain rather than single joint pain, and individuals' initial treatment approach, with painkillers being the most common (53%) and physiotherapy being the least common (0%).

This study shows a low level of awareness about physiotherapy among rural residents and their initial treatment approach for musculoskeletal pain caused by a highly challenging occupational environment. Despite the prevalence of such health issues, people's first response is to take painkillers, which only provide temporary relief and do not address the underlying cause of pain.

Comparison with other studies:

Paul et al., 2015⁷ conducted a study that examined physiotherapy awareness around the globe in nations with high and low development index. Even in high-development countries, the survey discovered a dearth of understanding regarding physiotherapy. However, considerable changes have been witnessed in India's metropolitan regions since 2015, as described by a variety of publications.^{7, 8}

The finding of the study emphasizes the need to raise awareness about physiotherapy in rural communities. Health professional may also get involved in awareness drives for all and at all levels globally because we only look for things we know about.^{9,10} Educating people about the benefits of physiotherapy and making it easily accessible in rural areas (primary healthcare) could help improve their quality of life and reduce dependency on pain medications.

Limitations: A more robust design with a larger sample size can be used in future studies.

CONCLUSION

We declare no conflict of interest.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Sharda University's community connect survey questionnaire was used to collect the data. We declare no conflict of interest.

Funding:

No funding has been received for this paper.

Ethical Clearance:

By the Institutional committee for community care. The paper was part of a community connect, and the institutional committee granted ethical clearance.

REFERENCES

1. Melariri, Herbert I et al. "Training, Attitudes, and Practice (TAP) among healthcare professionals in the Nelson Mandela Bay municipality, South Africa: A health promotion and disease prevention perspective." *PloS one* vol. 16,11 e0259884. 24 Nov. 2021, DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0259884](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0259884)
2. Ssemata, Andrew Sentoogo et al. "Exploring the barriers to healthcare access among persons with disabilities: a qualitative study in rural Luuka district, Uganda." *BMJ open* vol. 14,11 e086194. 2 Nov. 2024, DOI: [10.1136/bmjopen-2024-086194](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2024-086194)
3. Dash, S.S., 2019. Awareness of physiotherapy & its scope among women in a community: a survey. *Int J Physiother Res*, 2014. 7(6), pp.3331-35. DOI: [10.16965/ijpr.2019.198](https://doi.org/10.16965/ijpr.2019.198)
4. Fernandes, Jorida; Bandekar, Sanjana. Obstacles in Obtaining Optimal Physiotherapy Services for Musculoskeletal Conditions in Rural Communities of Goa: A Cross-sectional Study. *Indian Journal of Physical Therapy and Research* 6(1):p 60-64, Jan-Jun 2024. DOI: [10.4103/ijptr.ijptr.16.23](https://doi.org/10.4103/ijptr.ijptr.16.23)
5. Mullerpattan, Rajani et al. "Pilot implementation of rural rehabilitation services, India." *Bulletin of the World Health Organization* vol. 100,11 (2022): 662-668. DOI: [10.2471/BLT.22.288168](https://doi.org/10.2471/BLT.22.288168)
6. Bolarinde, Samuel Olufemi; Owoyemi, Temitope Victor; Obaya, Ayodeji Ojo; Nanimebila, Michael. Awareness and perception of physiotherapy practice among career educators in selected secondary schools in Nigeria. *Muller Journal of Medical Sciences and Research* 11(2):p 65-70, Jul-Dec 2020. | DOI: [10.4103/mjmsr.mjmsr.8.20](https://doi.org/10.4103/mjmsr.mjmsr.8.20)
7. PMbada, C., Olawuyi, A., Oyewole, O.O. et al. Characteristics and determinants of community physiotherapy utilization and supply. *BMC Health Serv Res* 19, 168 (2019). DOI. [10.1186/s12913-019-3994-4](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-019-3994-4)
8. Gupta, Garima, and Nupur Nandini. "Prevalence of low back pain in non working rural housewives of Kanpur, India." *International journal of occupational medicine and environmental health* vol. 28,2 (2015): 313-20. DOI: [10.13075/ijomeh.1896.00299](https://doi.org/10.13075/ijomeh.1896.00299)
9. GBD 2023 Disease and Injury and Risk Factor Collaborators. "Burden of 375 diseases and injuries, risk-attributable burden of 88 risk factors, and healthy life expectancy in 204 countries and territories, including 660 subnational locations, 1990-2023: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2023." *Lancet* (London, England) vol. 406,10513 (2025): 1873-1922. DOI: [10.1016/S0140-6736\(25\)01637-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(25)01637-X)
10. Vikas, K., Public Awareness Towards Physiotherapy: A Survey (Master's thesis, Rajiv Gandhi University of Health Sciences (India)).2013. ProQuest Dissertations & Theses, 2013. 30559357. <https://www.proquest.com/openview/f130d3c6ed07fe5357371528a9add82e/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=2026366&diss=y>